

String Theory - The Devil's Gift - 8T

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September 18, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T which allowed deriving the primordial, the author analyzes the greatest pitfall of modern physics. Which is the idea of String theory, which allocate a particle to each mode of energy, the author goes via that idea of String theory to prove why it can't be right, and why theory of that sort can be considered the worst idea in the history of physics.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by conditions below (1). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the idea that stands at the heart of String theory. If one understood correctly, each "mode of vibration" of the string is isomorphic to a particle of certain kind. The more volatile the vibration the higher the energy. The string has infinite potential geometrical combinations and knots. That core idea according to the 8T author is wrong. First, if it was correct there would not be a standard model, as slight variations of the string would account in a bound state of the proton and the neutron, they would not form an abelian group but rather a non-abelian group with infinite kind of particles. Second, it is impossible to derive the action or the Lagrangian of such a theory, as it is impossible to derive which state out of the infinite set of states of the string should have minimal energy or considered stationary string. It is not promised that the string will stay at the lowest state of vibration. String theory is impossible to work with, its core idea is flawed. It is impossible to make any sort of prediction assuming that is the case, let alone any laws of nature or reasoning. If that theory was correct there would be infinite bound state of matter, not just nine combinations as found with the omega minus. It has been built almost 60 years ago, many average mind physicists worked on it and the result is no testable predictions were made at all. To map the scope of theory, one will have to map all over the combinations of the string and associate each geometrical pattern to a particle. How can that even be done? that idea is ridiculous as there are infinite variations, an suppose that was correct, the variation of the string is impossible to predict, so even if one can map N combinations, each combinations have infinite morphism options.

They could be more volatile, such variations would than yield measureable variations in the coupling magnitude, or alternatively infinite coupling magnitudes. If it were correct, we would measure infinite bound states of the electron, photon, and hadrons. It is the opposite of a Lagrangian oriented, as it implies nature would generate infinite couplings with no reason behind it, in contrast to the 8T which gives a exact reason to the magnitudes of the couplings, particles, and each universes (as they have many solutions) could have a different set of laws, that is "standard model of its own". How many laws nature would generate? Why bother to create so many set of distinct particles for each universe, it is a instead of just one?. In the 8T because of the invariance of the prime ring, the same magnitudes, and Bosons appear at all the manifolds at the same order, the dominating forces are depended upon the unique arrow of the manifold, as it gets older the weaker interactions are more common, as it close to singularity the strong forces are dominating creating the hadrons. All manifolds have Quarks in them in decreasing total mass order, all universes are obeying the same laws, nets are primes and interacting via areas of extremum curvatures flattening each other, and of the same kind. There exist one equation for all, one principle - a varying manifold in a packet. That is it and to prove it the primorial was yielded. Is there a stronger equations than (1.41) or (1) in string theory in terms of the spectra and accuracy of predictions? To put it another way, String theory is the devils gift. It is a dead end theory, which makes simple things complicated as build upon the implicit assumption that those infinitesimal things, i.e. particles are important. It shifts the center of attention to the object rather to the principles and to the ideas, it gives no testable predictions, it is long and hard to comprehend, it predicts no law, it is not Lagrangian oriented in any way, and many below average to average brain physicists worked on it without aligning it with anything in the particle scales, nor in the cosmological scales. It should have no place in physics anymore, 8T is far superior by all means, predictions wise it has much more predictions, which are correct, and length wise it is much shorter, it is also easier to comprehend. 8T was built upon one subject of describing which yielded all the other infinitesimal quantities and the equation which results in Dark energy and flatness, string theory is built upon describing an infinite set of states of a varying infinitesimal object that yielded not a single prediction in sixty plus years, in any scale infinitesimal nor cosmological and it uses measured values such as Planck and the speed of light to reach the coupling magnitudes rather than deriving them from pure thought, as presented in the 8T.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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